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ABSTRACT

Introduction: This case report presents the history and management of a 67-year-old male patient with a rare variant of coronary artery anomalies, "RCA originating from the LAD". The patient had additional risk factors such as diabetes, hypertension and a history of percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) of the LAD and RCA.

Case Presentation: After recurrent chest pains, investigations revealed multiple stenoses in the LAD and CX as well as RCA originating from the LAD. Because of this rare anomaly of origin and multiple critical stenoses, the patient underwent triple coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). The patient recovered clinically on the fifth postoperative day and was recommended regular follow-up and medical treatment before discharge.

Discussion: According to literature data, coronary artery anomalies occur in approximately 0.6 - 1.5% of the general population, and some of them may lead to severe ischemic events or sudden cardiac death. The origin of the RCA from the LAD is a very rare variant in this picture, reported only in 0.02 - 0.05% of angiography series. The course of the anomaly and the presence of associated lesions may affect the prognosis.

Conclusion: In this case, surgical intervention successfully treated the patient and prevented ischemic complications. The main message of this case is that rare coronary anomalies, especially when associated with severe stenoses, are of high clinical importance and early diagnosis and appropriate treatment have a favorable impact on the longterm prognosis of patients.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

RCA arising from LAD, coronary artery anomaly, coronary bypass surgery (CABG), percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI).

INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery anomalies are cardiac anomalies that, despite their relatively low prevalence in the general population, can have clinically important consequences. The most common coronary anomalies include abnormal origin and course of the right coronary artery (RCA). The origin of the RCA from the left coronary system (especially from the left anterior descending artery, LAD) is an extremely rare variation and may predispose to severe ischemic events or sudden cardiac problems in some cases. In this case report, we describe a 67-year-old male patient with a history of known coronary artery disease (CAD) who was successfully discharged after coronary bypass surgery for RCA anomaly arising from the LAD.

CASE PRESENTATION

Demographic Information and History

- Age/sex: 67-year-old male patient.
- Comorbidities: Diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension (HT), anxiety disorder, benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH).
- Cardiac History: Previously diagnosed coronary artery disease, history of percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) to both LAD and RCA. It was learned that the patient had not used antiaggregants for a long time.

The patient had irregular cardiology visits in the last year and was found to have discontinued the recommended antithrombotic treatment. Recently, he presented to the emergency department several times with complaints of chest pain and sweating, and the result of Myocardial Perfusion Scintigraphy (MPS) performed in one of these visits was reported as normal. However, new tests were planned due to recurrent complaints.

Physical Examination and Laboratory Findings

- Physical Examination: Vital signs were stable (blood pressure 130/80 mmHg, pulse 80/min, respiratory rate and O₂ saturation within normal limits). No abnormal murmur was detected on cardiac auscultation.
- Laboratory Values: Triglycerides: 287 mg/dL (high) and Hb: 11 g/dL (mild anemia)

Imaging and Cardiology Evaluation

- Echocardiography (ECHO): Ejection fraction (EF) was 55%. Evaluation for segmental wall motion abnormality (SWMD) revealed no significant segmental abnormality despite suboptimal visualization.
- Coronary Angiography Findings:
 - LMCA (Left Main Coronary Artery): Normal.
 - LAD (Left Anterior Descending Artery): 80-90% stenosis was observed in the mid segment; 60-70% stenosis was present in the previously stented area. The distal segment was plaque.
 - CX (Circumflex Artery): Mid segment plaque, 70% stenosis at OM3 ostial.
 - RCA: The right coronary artery was seen to arise from the LAD and a 70% stenosis was reported in the ostial area.

Because of this rare anomaly (RCA originating from the LAD) and multiple stenoses, the patient was referred to the cardiovascular surgery council for coronary bypass surgery.

Surgical Intervention and Postoperative Process

- Operation: The patient underwent "Coronary Artery Bypass Graft (CABG)" for three vessels (LAD, CX and RCA of abnormal origin). Saphenous vein and/or Internal Mammary Artery (IMA) grafts were used.
- Postoperative Follow-up: On the fifth postoperative day, the patient's general condition was good, hemodynamic parameters were stable and no major abnormality was detected on pulmonary examination. The surgical incisions were clean and healing was uneventful. The patient started to gradually return to daily activities by increasing mobilization.
- Discharge: Approximately one week after surgery, the patient was discharged uneventfully with an outpatient follow-up scheduled ten days later.

(Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for the publication of this case report and any accompanying images.)

DISCUSSION

General Prevalence of Coronary Artery Anomalies

- In large series of patients in the general population (e.g., Yamanaka and Hobbs' 1990 coronary angiography study of 126,595 patients), the overall incidence of coronary artery anomalies ranged from approximately 0.6 to 1.5% (Yamanaka & Hobbs, 1990).
- While some of these anomalies may remain clinically silent, especially those with a so-called "malignant course" may pose a life-threatening risk.

- Most Common Coronary Anomalies
- Separate Ostium of the LAD and LCX Separated from the Left Main Coronary Artery (LMCA)
- Origin of the Right Coronary Artery (RCA) from the Left Sinus of Valsalva (or left coronary sinus)
- Exit of the Circumflex Artery (LCX) from the Right Sinus Valsalva or RCA Ostium
- Exit of the Left Main Coronary Artery (LMCA) from the Right Sinus of Valsalva

RCA Exiting the LAD: A Rare Anomaly

- Origin of the RCA from the LAD is one of the most rarely reported coronary anomalies in the literature. Origin of the RCA from the left coronary system (especially from the LAD) is reported in angiographic studies at very low rates of 0.02-0.05% (even lower in some series) (Roberts, 1986).
- Despite such rarity, the exact course of the abnormality (e.g. interarterial, intramyocardial, etc.) and the presence of additional stenoses may be prognostically decisive.
- RCA originating from the LAD may sometimes be associated with additional bifurcation anomalies or ostial stenoses. Therefore, coronary angiography or CT angiography findings should be analyzed in detail.

Clinical Significance and Risks

- Coronary anomalies may be detected incidentally in some patients; in others, they may lead to a serious clinical picture, such as myocardial ischemia, arrhythmia, syncope or sudden cardiac death.
- In these cases, the course of the coronary arteries is of great importance. Especially if the anomaly is located between the aorta and the pulmonary artery (interarterial course), it is considered higher risk.
- For rare anomalies (e.g. RCA arising from the LAD), the strategy for surgical or percutaneous intervention is determined by the patient's symptoms, additional stenoses, evidence of ischemia and risk factors.

In this case, a 67-year-old male patient with a rare coronary anomaly -right coronary artery (RCA) originating from the left anterior descending artery (LAD)- underwent successful coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) due to multiple significant stenoses. The surgical approach was necessary given the severity of the lesions and the high risk of ischemic complications. Postoperatively, the patient showed a good clinical recovery, with stable hemodynamic parameters and no significant complications. He was discharged approximately one week after surgery with recommendations for regular follow-up.

CONCLUSION

The rarity of RCA originating from the LAD (0.02-0.05% incidence in angiographic series) underscores the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate intervention. In this case, surgical treatment effectively managed the anomaly and associated stenoses, preventing potential life-threatening ischemic events. The findings highlight the necessity of individualized treatment plans for patients with coronary artery anomalies to improve long-term prognosis (Angelini, 2007; Roberts, 1986).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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